

PROSPECTS FOR DOING BUSINESS ON THE BASIS OF THE CONSTITUTION OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Annotation. In the articles, forerunners on the domestic economy in agriculture are based on.

Key words. Soybeans, innovations, innovative technologies, seeds, next generation soybeans. Chorian countries.

One of the most important scales of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to fully satisfy the demand of the population for food. In achieving this goal, it is important to grow grain and leguminous crops, increase their assortment, and improve their quality.

An important indicator determining the scientific and scientific and technical potential of scientific institutions is the availability and armament of their basic funds. Analysis of these indicators in scientific institutions of the Khorizh states shows ambiguity.

The cultivation of soybean variety among field crops is associated with the rich biochemical composition of these seeds and, first of all, with the high amount of complete protein in the composition of a complete amino acid, the ability to grow it using grain and broadband technologies, the ability to produce it in its own way, due to the symbiotic fixation of nitrogen from atmospheric air. Soybean crops, as well as soybean cultivation on all continents of the planet, have particular flexibility to the different growth conditions that are growing in the region. The affordable source of protein nutrition, soybeans, the most valuable component of feed, is the most important component of many pharmaceuticals and cosmetics, successfully demonstrates the growing social importance.

It is the oldest cultivated plant that has appeared and is widespread in the Indian region. Over the years, it has been recognized for growing soybeans in large areas of America and Europe. The world has seen a steady increase in soybean cultivation.

This is due to the versatility of the use of soybean crops for technical, feed and food purposes; high yields due to rising grain prices due to excess demand over supply; simple cultivation to produce a useful crop.

In recent years, the demand for soybeans has grown in Russia. Along with the traditional Far Eastern region, it began to spread in the Central States, regions and regions of the European part of the country, as well as in the south of

Western Siberia, the Urals and Altai. However, the total volume of soybean cultivation in Russia remains extremely low to meet the needs of the national economy for highly toxic raw materials, covering them by only 20-30%.

In this regard, the import of soybeans and meal from the United States of America continues. But it has sufficient natural resources, rich scientific potential and best practice, allows you to increase the production of soybeans by 8-10 times; and in the future, not only fully meet your needs for it, but also export environmentally friendly (genetically unchanged) soybean exports to European countries at affordable prices, as demand for such products has increased.

The comprehensive importance of the shadow, the state and reserves of increasing production are expressed especially in the Russian region. The use of these opportunities will make it possible to achieve significant success in the cultivation of soybeans and put Russia and European countries in the first place among all other countries in the production of soybeans.

In Russia, the main production volumes of soybeans and soybeans continue to grow. This is due to the demand of the food and feed industry for plant protein. In connection with the definition of centralized tasks for the accelerated development of the livestock industry, there are important prospects for the growth of this market. At the same time, the issue of developing a mechanism for increasing the production of cultural soybeans at the expense of the country's internal reserves remains relevant.

Soybean seed production is the basis for realizing the potential of biological natural productivity of this variety.

In obtaining friendly soybean seed jackets and increasing yields, the role of breeding quality of seeds is certainly important. In all respects, high-quality seeds are the basis for high productivity of soybean crops. Therefore, the main task of growing seeds is to obtain seeds with high breeding and planting properties. Its main task is to maintain in the growing process all the characteristics of the variety at the same level as when they are passed for varietal testing.

Soybeans provide a typical of at least 99.5 percent for elite seeds, 98.5 percent for propagation seeds used for seed crops, and 98.0 percent for seeds intended for marketable areas. Their outflow in these categories should be at least 87.0 percent, respectively; 82.0 percent and 80 percent; purity - not less than 98.0 percent; 96.0 percent and 95.0 percent; impurities of other seeds, not more than

10, 15 and 25 pieces per 1 kg, including 5, 8, 15 pieces/kg of weeds. Moisture content of seeds during storage shall not exceed 14%.

Seed sowing purity is achieved during the growing season, that is, 2 times during the flowering and ripening period, and 1 time in industrial seed production, improving the variety treatment carried out in the early stages of genetic diversity. During the cleaning process, according to morphological features, atypical plants are removed from crops, flower color, bean color, seeds and their traces; growth; sick and damaged samples. Before testing the crops, various cleaning is completed and rejected plants are removed from the field.

Testing of seed crops serves as the main process for assessing the purity of the variety, is carried out by specially prepared agronomist-aproborators and, according to its results, the compiled documents serve as a legal document for the certification of seeds.

Primary cultivation of soybean seeds is carried out in scientific institutions under the control of the authors of the original tribe and ends with the cultivation of the required number of original seeds.

Elite seeds obtained from seed planting must be intended for seed crops in scientific institutions, seed plants or in large farming and dehkan farms licensed for seed cultivation and cultivation. The first and second reproductions can be used in commercial cultures. Soybean varieties must be renewed while preserving mass reproductions from seed sowing. The genetic purity of diversity depends not only on the time of reproduction, but also on compliance with agrotechnical requirements when growing seeds and bringing them into a sowing state during midday work, as well as on the prevention of mechanical blockage of varieties.

Mechanical purity of seeds is ensured by selection of feathers corresponding to sizes of seeds during primary and secondary purification. On final revision, they remove seeds of grass and other cultivated plants, seeds of broken, sensitive, immature and diseased soybeans. Seeds are sorted by size and specific mass simultaneously with harvesting. For sowing, the largest 1 and 2 fractions of seeds are used, the yield of which ranges from 60 to 80 percent. Such seeds are highly productive and inoculate.

Seeds are stored in dry ventilated warehouses, consist of 7-8 bags in original and elite bags, massively increase on rocks up to 1.5 m high. During the storage period, twice, in autumn and spring, analyzes of the quality of their sowing are carried out.

Typical methods of growing soybeans in seed crops date back to the usual sowing period later (in the conditions of the North Caucasus - the second half of June and the first for the middle season for early cell varieties), which avoids the harmful effects of the August drought and heat. Seed extinction; as well as the maximum collection period (with humidity up to 15-16 percent), prevention of excessive rise, as well as a decrease in the quality of their sowing due to greater infection with diseases. Soy seed care, prevention of the spread of foreign grass, pests and diseases on them by timely mechanical and chemical treatment should be carried out more carefully. With a delay in the release of mid-season varieties, a seed humidity of 35-40 percent, such crops can be desiccated with reglone (2 l/ha each). This event is especially important for seeding.

Literature:

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